

A smart-sensing AI-driven platform for scalable, low-cost hydroponic units

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ACRONYMS LIST

FW	Fresh Weight
DW	Dry Weight
GP	Growing Period
LED	Light Emitting Diode
NS	Nutrient Solution
PPFD	Photosynthetic Photon Flux Density
PFD	Photon Flux Density
PAR	Photosynthetically Active Radiation
E-PAR	Extended Photosynthetically Active Radiation
24VHELED	24-Volt High Efficiency Light Emitting Diode
HFR	High Far-Red
HR	High Red
NG	No Green
HBG	High Blue and Green
CRBD	Complete Random Block Design
PPM	Parts Per Million
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
RH	Relative Humidity

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Microgreens are plants at the young phenological stage between sprouts and baby greens, with a growing period of around 6-16 days from germination to harvest. They are gaining increasing attention because of their short production cycle, dense growing conditions, and their beneficial attributes such as high nutrient density, secondary metabolite content, and gastronomic applications, all of which contribute to their categorization and use as ‘functional foods.’ However, the degree and impact of environmental parameterization on Microgreens production is not firmly established, with some crucial gaps such as light recipes being of critical importance. This is of contemporary importance given the current energy crisis; identifying pathways to reduce energy use and evaluate outcomes for production efforts can have beneficial impacts. With this in mind, the objective of this deliverable was to investigate experimentally the effects of nutrient solution fertilization, seeding density, and light spectrum combinations and intensities on fresh weight and dry weight accumulation in four Microgreen species and varieties: *Sinapis alba* (Mustard var. White Candy), *Brassica oleracea* var. *sabellica* L. (Kale var. Black Mandingo), *Brassica oleracea* (Radish var. Daikon Panzer), and *Brassica oleracea* convar. *acephala* var. *gongylodes* L. (Kohlrabi var. Red Cardinal). Our objective was to evaluate 10 different growth environments in highly controlled experiments conducted in a Climate Chamber in the University of Copenhagen’s Taastrup Campus, Taastrup, Denmark. The results of these experiments have shown that there are significant differences between light recipes for both FW and DW biomass accumulation. Furthermore, there were differences between seeding density, light type, and fertilization as well for FW and DW biomass accumulation. We have shown the degree of these differences for each of our four Brassicaceae Microgreen species. Overall, the best light recipe was the High Far-Red, which produced the best outcomes. This was a very strong relationship for FW, but for DW, there was more variety for light recipe influences. The effect of fertilization was also very clear, as it improved fresh biomass accumulation by around 1.5-2.0 times depending on the light recipe used. We have also presented results on the production of biomass per unit dollar input. We showed that the 24VHELEDs were much more economically productive than the highly expensive OSRAM research lights. Furthermore, their ease of use, waterproof qualities, low weight, and durability, led us to the conclusion that they are the better choice for growers in almost all cases; therefore, we recommend environmental recipes 9 and 10 for use by Microgreen growers. Furthermore, although there was a general improvement to FW biomass of about 1.13 times via using the more expensive OSRAM lights (recipes 1-8), they are around 50 times less productive per unit dollar input than the 24VHELEDs. In sum, therefore, we recommend growers use 24VHELEDs of a similar recipe to ours used here, which had a high green and red component; however, our research also demonstrated the efficacy of using light recipes with a high component of Far-Red light. Therefore, an ideal combination would be finding 24VHELEDs that also have Far-Red bands included in their light recipe, to approximate our HFR recipe, which had best overall productivity. Furthermore, photons with larger wavelengths have lower energy requirements per photon; therefore, using light recipes with higher amounts of Red or Far-Red light can lower energy costs of light recipes. Overall, we showed that Microgreens

were sensitive to their environmental inputs, and we have contextualized the outputs for both overall production and for relative production metrics to offer valuable insight into Microgreen production options.

1 INTRODUCTION

Microgreens are plants harvested at the young phenological stage between sprouts and baby greens, with a growing period of around 6-16 days from germination to harvest. Many plants cultivated for human consumption at a mature stage can also be harvested at a younger stage as a Microgreen. In practice, there are currently around 80-100 commonly cultivated species of Microgreens used for human consumption (Ying et al., 2020a, 2020b, 2020c). However, there exists a large variety of Microgreens suitability to the specific conditions associated with indoor hydroponic production, with some species cultivated more often than others. The most commonly cultivated species are from the Brassicaceae family, which includes Broccoli, Cabbage, Arugula, Kale, and Mustard, to name a few examples (Björkman et al., 2011). Microgreens are increasingly gaining attention because of their short production cycle, tolerance to dense growing conditions, and their beneficial attributes such as high nutrient density, secondary metabolite content, and gastronomic applications, all of which contribute to their categorization and use as ‘functional foods.’ However, the degree and impact of environmental parameterization on Microgreens production is not firmly established, with some crucial gaps such as light recipes being of critical importance. This is of contemporary importance given the current energy crisis; identifying pathways to reduce energy use, improve spatial use, and evaluate different outcomes and tradeoffs for production efforts can have beneficial impacts.

In general, Microgreens production takes place indoors with varying degrees of environmental parameterization. The most important environmental factors to control are day-length (photoperiod), which can be augmented by lights to ensure growth cueing via photoreceptor stimulation; having a relatively stable Day/Night temperature around 21/17 °C for optimal physiological function; controlling relative humidity, CO₂, dissolved oxygen, air flow, nutrient solution pH and EC, and fertilization; and carefully choosing the type of light used (quality and quantity) depending on desired outcomes. Controlling for these environmental factors offers key advantages: firstly, it allows year-round production, as there is no dependence on natural photoperiod or light cues; secondly, the disease and competition burden is lessened; thirdly, it allows targeted delivery of resources viz. water, nutrients, and light. It is also important to discuss the method of delivering these resources, which can be achieved by many of the most common hydroponic systems that are used today, although the most commonly used systems for Microgreens are ‘drip’ and ‘ebb and flow’ systems because Microgreens have smaller roots than mature plants and grow at a much higher density, thereby making these hydroponic systems more suitable for their production:

1. **Ebb and flow** uses an external reservoir that is pumped and drained through the growing medium at regular timed intervals to deliver water/nutrients to the plants; the ebb and flow allows for oxygenation of roots and the medium when pumps are not running, as roots are exposed to the air
2. **Drip** systems are most appropriate for large-scale industrial processes; they apply the NS at regular or nearly continuous intervals in the root zone through narrow pipes that allows for nutrient uptake and ample oxygenation of the roots.

3. **Nutrient film technique**, uses a nutrient delivery system with pumps, where a thin film of nutrient is flowing at regular intervals in pipes, making the nutrients available for easy uptake and ample oxygenation of roots.

4. **Wicking** systems use a medium that can absorb the nutrient solution and make it available to the plants and hence the medium ‘wicks’ or moves water via diffusion from the solution to the growing substrate and the plants.

5. **Deep water culture** uses a reservoir of nutrient solution (NS) where the plants are grown in a floating medium and roots are immersed in NS. Root oxygenation is an issue due to limited spaces between the floating medium and the nutrient solution and requires an airstone.

6. **Aeroponics**, consists of spraying nutrient solutions with a fine mist on suspended plant roots with a spraying pump to supply the nutrients and oxygenate roots for optimal plant growth.

Beyond the movement of water, oxygen, and nutritional resources via hydroponic systems, the Microgreens have to be grown in an appropriate medium, known as substrate, that has enough porosity, strength, durability, and will not leach harmful compounds to ensure effective growth and food-safe production. Some examples of ideal substrates are coconut coir, polyethylene terephthalate, peat moss, cellulose, or even gauze, to name a few examples, which we have shown in Table 1 below. Another important category of growth environment parameterization is light. This is currently the focus of most recent research, as the influence of different spectra (quality) and amount (quantity) of light on production outputs is currently of great interest for optimizing Microgreen production outcomes and identifying tradeoffs. Some examples of these tradeoffs are discussed in D1.1. Although parameterization to some degree is necessary, Microgreen production can be achieved on a continuum of technological and capital input; a shelf or series of shelves in an office with ambient climate control, a grow tent with circulating fan, an industrial warehouse with highly controlled environmental parameters, and a climate-controlled research growth chamber, are all possible methods of keeping the environmental parameters in check to greater or lesser degrees. Achieving specific Microgreen production outcomes can be manipulated via a variety of methods along this technological input continuum. Therefore, we designed these experiments to evaluate some tradeoffs of using different types of inputs to evaluate their influence on Microgreen production outputs. This was done using the metrics of total production and relative production for Fresh Weight (FW) and Dry Weight (DW) accumulation, as well as cost accounting, to help inform Microgreen producers about relevant key production tradeoffs. In combination with other project deliverables, this will begin to outline some of the dynamics between controlled and uncontrolled systems (D1.2 and D4.3), as well as between biomass and secondary metabolite production (D1.2 and D4.2).

Table 1. List of commonly used substrates for Microgreens and corresponding reference examples.

Substrate Type	Example Reference
30% compost, 30% peat, 30% coir, 10% perlite	Gerovac et al., 2016
Sphagnum peat moss	Samuoliene et al., 2017
Coconut fiber (coir)	Kong et al., 2020
Polyethylene terephthalate fiber	Craver et al., 2015
Gauze	Zhang et al., 2019

Peat moss and Rockwool	Kamal et al., 2020
General purpose soil	Lobiuc et al., 2017

In sum, among the environmental parameters for Microgreen production under controlled conditions, light spectrum combinations and intensities (quality and quantity, respectively) are key factors of contemporary interest affecting fresh and dry biomass accumulation. Furthermore, the choice to fertilize Microgreens with a Nutrient Solution (NS) or use only water can also affect Microgreen growth. Finally, the density of seed sowing is a tradeoff between spatial use efficiency and competition dynamics between individual Microgreens. Hence, the objective of this deliverable was to investigate experimentally the effects of light spectrum combinations, NS fertilization, and seeding density on Fresh Weight (FW) and Dry Weight (DW) biomass accumulation in four Microgreen species and varieties within the Brassicaceae family: *Sinapis alba* (Mustard var. White Candy), *Brassica oleracea* var. *sabellica* L. (Kale var. Black Mandingo), *Brassica oleracea* (Radish var. Daikon Panzer), and *Brassica oleracea* convar. *acephala* var. *gongylodes* (Kohlrabi var. Red Cardinal).

The objective of Deliverable 1.2 was to evaluate 10 different growth environments in controlled experiments conducted in a Climate Chamber in the University of Copenhagen's Taastrup Campus located in Taastrup, Denmark. As shown in Table 2, by varying three production parameters viz. light spectrum recipes (five different recipes from two different types of lights), Nutrient Solution (yes or no fertilizer), and seeding density, we can track the influence of these parameters on downstream production outcomes such as Fresh Weight and Dry Weight (kg/m²) accumulation per unit area. Identifying the influence of these different factors can be used by Microgreen producers to help make production decisions based on their species of choice, desired outcomes, and the resources available for use. We have constructed the environmental recipes in Table 2 by varying these three key parameters, while maintaining a consistent Photoperiod at 16 hours, Growing Period at 8 days, Relative Humidity at 65%, Temperature at 21 °C, pH at 6.5, and Electrical Conductivity (EC) at 1.80 for fertilized NS, and 6.5 pH and 0.78 EC for non-fertilized NS. CO₂ concentration (ppm) was measured, but it was not a parameter we could control in our climate chamber.

Table 2. List of 10 experimental environmental recipes for investigating optimal Microgreen production for selected species.

RECIPE NUMBER	LIGHT RECIPE	FERTILIZER	SEEDING DENSITY
1	High Far-Red	Yes	Low, Standard, Middle, High
2	High Far-Red	No	Low, Standard, Middle, High
3	High Blue and Green	Yes	Low, Standard, Middle, High
4	High Blue and Green	No	Low, Standard, Middle, High
5	High Red	Yes	Low, Standard, Middle, High
6	High Red	No	Low, Standard, Middle, High
7	No Green	Yes	Low, Standard, Middle, High
8	No Green	No	Low, Standard, Middle, High
9	24VHELED	Yes	Low, Standard, Middle, High
10	24VHELED	No	Low, Standard, Middle, High

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 EXPERIMENTAL CONTEXT

After we researched the general parameter requirements for the growth environment conditions from our literature review in D1.1, we then designed our experimental conditions. Our first step was acquiring a growth chamber at the University of Copenhagen's Taastrup Campus, Taastrup, Denmark. This experiment was conducted in a 'Convicon CMP5090' climate chamber (Figure 1) with programmable conditions set to daily (24-hour) schedules located at the University of Copenhagen's Taastrup Campus, Taastrup, Denmark. This climate chamber allowed for the control of temperature, airflow, and power inputs via its climate control system. Within the climate chamber, we constructed a six-tiered growing system, supplied by a commercial Microgreen producer, Instagreen (Instagreen.eu, Barcelona, Spain; Figure 2). The Instagreen grow system is 217.5 cm in height, 120 cm wide, and 112 cm deep. This growing system can hold up to 12 trays on six layers (2 trays per layer), with a total usable growing space of 7.26 m². Each growing tray has the dimensions of 110 (L) x 55 (W) x 5 (H) cm. 40 cups fit per tray, with each cup having a top dimension of 14.5 (L) x 10 (W) cm, with a narrower bottom dimension of 11.5 (L) x 8.2 (W) cm, and a cup height of 5 cm. The Instagreen setup is a modular system with variable-height layers that are tilted slightly to direct water flow via gravity after being pumped to the top-most layer from a reservoir. The solution then descends from one layer to the next via perforations in the bottom-most section of each tray and falls over a slide into the top of the next layer, until it returns to the reservoir. The reservoir holds approximately 40 liters of solution at a maximum.

Figure 1. Exterior image of the Convicon CMP5090 Climate Chamber at the University of Copenhagen's Taastrup Campus, Taastrup, Denmark.

Figure 2 (Left). Interior image of the Instagreen Professional Cultivation System with 6 layers of grow trays inside our Climate Chamber in Taastrup, Denmark.

Figure 3 (Right). Example photo the Instagreen Professional Cultivation System with various Microgreens species nearing harvest time (photo credit: Instagreen.eu).

Our experimental design was to use the upper three layers as growing spaces as seen in Figure 2, with the top-most layer using three OSRAM Phytofy Research Lights (Osram, Beverley, MA, USA) that were 41 cm from the emitters to the surface of the trays, the second layer being a buffer, and the third layer using four 1 meter long High Efficiency 24-volt LED (24VHELED) lights equidistant from one another which were 32 cm from the surface of the trays. The bottom three layers were used as germination space to ensure a successful transition for germination, growth, harvest, and beginning the next generation. Each germination layer consisted of four standard growing trays, with two on the bottom, and two on the top, to create a high-humidity dark-zone for adequate germination. Within our Climate Chamber we used a centralized lockable utility box to ensure safe operations with electrical components shielded for use by growers and protected from water (Figure 4). In addition to the externally located climate control software, we also utilized two ‘Paladin pro4 Bluetooth’ timers which were located in the utility box inside the climate chamber. These were used to program schedules for the ‘Water Master 1800 liters/hour’ water pump and the 24VHELEDs using the ‘Save’n carry’ App for Android (Hugo-mueller.de). We programmed our grow system to be watered two times a day for 15 minutes,

8 hours apart during the 16 hour photoperiod, once at the beginning, and once 8 hours later. The 24VHELED lights were controlled using the second ‘Paladin pro4 Bluetooth’ timer, which ensures that the light has a 16 hour photoperiod parallel with the OSRAM lights. Within our climate chamber we also used a ‘Plus Zap’ infrared bug zapper to control pest incidence. We also used a sanitizing floor mat that was filled with ‘Rodalon’ (active ingredients: chloride-based compounds) that is safe to use with plastics. The first round of experiments was

conducted from May 12th to July 11th, while the second round was conducted from August 21st to October 14th.

Figure 4. Standard utility box housing our two timers, three power supplies for the OSRAM RLs, our MOXA port, the 24VHELED power supply, and green network cable connected to our router for remote control.

2.2 LIGHT CONDITIONS

Within horticultural terminology, light intensity is defined as the number of photons intercepted by the plant per unit area over time, which is generally referred to as Photosynthetic Photon Flux Density (PPFD) in units of micromoles per meter squared per second ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$), with photons within the wavelength range of 400-700 nm, which is the range of Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) (Xu, 2018). However, recent research (Zhen et al., 2021; Zhen & van Iersel, 2016) has challenged the traditional range of Photosynthetically active radiation, with research increasingly calling to include both UV-A (380 nm) and Far-Red (around 700-750 nm) in definitions of ‘useful’ light for plants. Therefore, because we have included Far-Red light components in our light recipes, we will describe our light conditions using Photon Flux Density (PFD), which describes all photons intercepted by the plants within the range of 380 to 800 nm. Furthermore, it is important to also consider the energy inputs per unit photon output: that is, not all photons are the same, as they have different

energy requirements at different wavelengths. For instance, red photons have a lower energy and higher number of photons compared to photons in the blue range. This is important to consider, as not all light recipes have the same cost in terms of energy inputs per unit output: a recipe high in blue light, for instance, will require more energy to produce the same number of photons compared to a recipe high in red photons. Another key metric for describing light conditions, therefore, is irradiance, which is the radiant flux of the received photons for a given unit of area, with the standard units of Watts per m². The link between irradiance and number of photons can be seen in Figure 5, which was calculated from our spectrometric measurements. It shows that the number of photons (μmol) that are produced each second per milliwatt of input energy at each wavelength

(350-800 nm) has a linear function with R²=1. This means that wavelengths in the UV and Blue region require more energy inputs to produce equivalent numbers of photons, as they have lower efficiency than wavelengths in the Green, Red, or Far-Red regions.

Figure 5. Regression for the efficiency of micromoles of photon generation per unit energy input, per second, for wavelengths of light from 350 to 800 nm. Linear equation and R² are displayed in upper right.

For our experimental setup, each layer in the grow system had three light treatment blocks: on layer 1, there were 3 OSRAM lights, with each one as a block; on layer 3, there were four lights, with 3 corresponding inter-light blocks of homogenous spectrum and intensity. The OSRAM lights have a max power draw of 150 Watts per fixture, with dimensions of 66.7 (W) x 29.9 (L) x 4.4 (H) cm per fixture. According to Osram, their lights have a total luminaire efficiency of 96.77%, with a total luminaire efficacy of 307936 μmol/s/W. Each emitter has a 0.1 Watt power draw. These lights have five channels with spectral peaks at 385 nm (UV-A, maximum emittance at 50 μmol/m²/s), 450 nm (Blue, maximum emittance at 250 μmol/m²/s), 521 nm (Green, maximum emittance at 100 μmol/m²/s), 660 nm (Red, maximum emittance at 250 μmol/m²/s), and 730 nm (Far-Red, maximum emittance at 100 μmol/m²/s), each peak of which can be set independently as a percent (0-100%) of its total output. There is also a sixth 'White' LED channel, which has a color temperature of 2,700 Kelvin, which is classified as between 'Sunrise and Sunset,' and has a maximum emittance of 250 μmol/m²/s. Therefore, the total maximum PFD for the OSRAM research light is 1000 μmol/m²/s. Figure 6 is a schematic detailing the distribution of emitters in the OSRAM light. It shows that there are a total of 154 emitters per light, with 77 per

Table 3. Spectrometric readings for our five light recipes which detail the specific band light intensities and resulting recipe component percentages, with total Daily Light Integral detailed for each as well. Four spectral bands were measured, at Blue (400-499 nm), Green (500-599 nm), Red (600-699 nm), and FR (700-800 nm). Values are shown as PFD ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$); and as a percentage of total light recipe.

Recipe	Blue (400-499 nm)	Green (500-599 nm)	Red (600-699 nm)	FR (700-800 nm)	Sum	Daily Light Integral (mol/m^2)
High Far-Red Light Recipe						
High Far-Red CRBD ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$)	53.43	60.30	93.30	61.96	268.99	15.49
High Far-Red CRBD (%)	19.86%	22.42%	34.69%	23.03%	100%	
No Green Light Recipe						
No Green CRBD ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$)	95.38	0.44	156.60	22.06	274.49	15.81
No Green CRBD (%)	34.75%	0.16%	57.05%	8.04%	100%	
High Red Light Recipe						
High Red CRBD ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$)	28.64	50.84	165.50	21.93	266.92	15.37
High Red CRBD (%)	10.73%	19.05%	62.01%	8.22%	100%	
High Blue and Green Light Recipe						
High Blue and Green CRBD ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$)	70.04	72.81	106.75	21.88	271.48	15.64
High Blue and Green CRBD (%)	25.80%	26.82%	39.32%	8.06%	100%	
24VHELEDs Light Recipe						
24VHELEDs CRBD ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$)	7.91	21.41	15.68	1.10	46.09	2.65
24VHELEDs CRBD (%)	17.16%	46.45%	34.02%	2.38%	100%	

Figure 7 below demonstrates the visualizations of the light recipes shown in Table 3. They show in detail the proportional contribution of each wavelength of light (in nanometers, nm), on the x-axis, to the overall recipe. The y-axis is a unitless scale (0-100%), which demonstrates the relative proportion of each nm of light compared to the maximum value. The white lines in each figure demonstrate the irradiance (W/m^2) of each light recipe, while the black curve shows the PFD, which considers the number of photons. This is an important demonstration of the difference between the light recipes, as they have similar numbers of photons per unit area, as shown in Table 3, but the Irradiance (energy) of the recipes differ based on their light components. Table 4 below expands on this by showing which light recipes were the most efficient. This is a combination of data seen in Figure 5 above and the light recipe schematics below. Each wavelength of light has a percentage of the total light recipe which was then multiplied by its corresponding efficiency value derived from the regression equation in Figure 5 above. Overall, the HR recipe was the most efficient recipe, followed closely by the HFR. The next most efficient recipe was the NG, with the HBG and the 24VHELED having the lowest efficiency values.

Table 4. Relative values for light recipe efficiency of total photon production. Highest efficiency is 1.00, with the other recipes being relative percentages. Calculations derived from Figure 5 and Table 3.

LIGHT RECIPE	OVERALL EFFICIENCY
HIGH BLUE AND GREEN	0.93
NO GREEN	0.96
HIGH RED	1.00
HIGH FAR-RED	0.98
24VHELED	0.92

Figure 7. Figures showing the relative values of irradiance (white lines) and PFD (black lines) for each light recipe used in our experiments. CRBD is Complete Random Block Design (CRBD), as these are derived from the spectrometric readings taken at the CRBD positions used in our experiments.

2.3 PLANT MATERIAL

Our genetic stock used for these experiments consisted of four species of Brassicaceae seeds which were purchased from Instagreen (Instagreen.eu, Barcelona, Spain), a commercial Microgreens production company. Specifically, we chose to experiment on Mustard (*Sinapis alba* cv. White Candy), Kale (*Brassica oleracea* var. *sabellica* L. cv. Black Mandingo), Radish (*Brassica oleracea* cv. Daikon Panzer), and Kohlrabi (*Brassica oleracea* convar. *Acephala* var. *gongylodes* L. cv. Red Cardinal). The seed names, their seeding density, 100 seed weight, and estimated seeds per cup for each sowing density can be seen in Table 5. These values are shown in Table 5, as a mean \pm the SE, with a sample size of six replicates per species for the 100 seed weights. The percent of seeds that were germinated were counted as well for each species over time. The value shown in Table 5 is the final germination value at harvest to detail the total achieved germination, eight days after sowing. Table 5 also shows the estimated amount of seeds per cup for our four different seeding densities (Low, Standard, Middle, and High). Overall, this table shows that we achieved very good germination results for all Microgreens at around 99%, while for Kohlrabi, the germination rate was around 91.5%. This was likely due to the seed source. However, overall we saw very good, uniform production of Kohlrabi, and it was not thought to impact the results, especially considering the low standard error for Kohlrabi germination rate.

Table 5. For all four species listed on the left, 100 seed weights (\pm standard error), seeding densities in grams per cup and estimated number of seeds per cup at each of the four densities (low, standard, middle, and high), and germination percentage (\pm standard error) are shown.

	100 Seed Weight (g)	Low (g/cup)	Est. Seeds/cup	Standard (g/cup)	Est. Seeds/cup	Middle (g/cup)	Est. Seeds/cup	High (g/cup)	Est. Seeds/cup	Germ %
Kohlrabi	0.161 \pm 0.005	1.125	697.03	1.500	929.37	1.875	1161.71	2.250	1394.05	91.45 \pm 0.36
Kale	0.313 \pm 0.004	1.725	551.82	2.300	735.76	2.875	919.71	4.000	1279.59	97.85 \pm 1.52
Mustard	0.720 \pm 0.011	2.250	312.67	3.000	416.90	3.750	521.12	4.500	625.35	99.81 \pm 0.03
Radish	1.325 \pm 0.021	3.000	226.38	4.000	301.84	5.000	377.30	6.000	452.76	99.69 \pm 0.05

For our experiment, the seeds were sown in plastic cups, with dimensions of 10 x 14.5 x 5 cm, on 100% cellulose growing pads according to sowing densities listed in Table 5. The substrate was soaked until saturated

with distilled water prior to sowing. None of the seeds were pre-soaked. However, after sowing seeds onto the soaked substrate, they were misted for approximately 1 second with distilled water to ensure initial moisture at the superior surface of the seeds. Our substrate was not compensated with a top-weight over the seeds, which was crucial for allowing the seedlings unimpeded vertical growth potential for short dark-zone germination and development time of 4 days. After sowing, each of the 8 cups were allocated according to a Complete Random Block Design (CRBD) for every light treatment. After this 4 day dark-germination period, the plants were put under the lights for 4 days of light treatments, and were therefore harvested 8 days after sowing.

2.4 ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS

To measure and record relative humidity (%) and air temperature (°C) we used two ‘TinyTag View2 Loggers’ (Gemini Data Loggers, UK), one located between layers 1 and 3, and the second between layer 4 and 6 to monitor changes in climate chamber microclimate. We used a ‘HOBO MX CO₂ Logger’ (Onset, USA) to measure CO₂ in our climate chamber. We also used a ‘HOBO Onset Pendant temp/light Logger’ (Onset, USA) to measure the amount of light (in lux units) and temperature directly under the OSRAM lights. Figure 8 below details the information collected from these devices for the first portion of our experiments: they show, from top to bottom, the CO₂ concentration (ppm), the Relative Humidity (%), and the temperature (°C). Overall, these panels in Figure 8 show that we achieved relatively stable environmental conditions. The variation in CO₂ was due to human activity in the climate chambers, but these spikes were quickly reduced down to their average value via air circulation. The RH also had some spikes due to our method of controlling humidity; overall, conditions were around 65%, which was our set point. The temperature was also relatively stable, although we did have a few weeks of heatwaves that caused temporary spikes in temperature, but it was not hotter than 23 degrees.

Figure 8. Panels showing the CO₂ concentration (top panel, parts per million), relative humidity (middle panel, %), and temperature (bottom panel, °C) for the high zone sensor location. X-axis shows the date for all three panels.

2.5 FERTILIZATION

For the fertilization component of our experiment, we used Pioneer NPK (Mg) Macro Blue 14-3-23 (3) (Pioneer, Denmark) for our macro nutrient fertilizer; for our micronutrient fertilizer, we used Pioneer Micro with Iron (Pioneer, Denmark). For the concentrated fertilizer solution, we used 10 kgs of Macro per 100 L of water, and 1 L of Micro per 100 L of water. For use in our hydroponic system, this was applied at 15% dilution for a rate of 85 mL of concentrated nutrient solution per 10 Liters of water. Table 6 details the initial percentages for both Macro and Micro solutions, and their corresponding concentration (in ppm) in our hydroponic solution. In addition, we used Nitric Acid to control our pH, with a Nutrient Solution pH target of 6.0. For EC, we did not modify it after achieving an initial value, with fertilization, of around of 1.8 mS/cm, according to our NS dilution. However, the pH was controlled daily with additional acid supplementation, which was necessary due to the high chalk (Calcium Carbonate, CaCO₃) content of Danish tap water. As water evaporates after irrigation runs using an ebb and flow system, it slowly deposits chalk on the trays, which increases the concentration of chalk after proceeding irrigation runs. Therefore, after every eight days (the generation time for the Microgreens) the system was drained of all solution, cleaned and scrubbed of residue, and reset with either Tap Water + Acid, or Tap Water + Fertilizer + Acid to obtain our pH and EC targets. This was done for both generations using fertilized NS and for unfertilized solution. Table 7 shows the average values of pH and EC over time. For measuring pH and Electrical Conductivity (EC, mS/cm), we used a Mesur Hand Instrument (Senmatic DGT-Voltmatic, Denmark), which has a sensitivity for pH of 0.1, and for EC has a sensitivity of 0.01 for EC values under 2.5 mS/cm.

Table 6. Fertilization details for the different macro- and micro-nutrient products used. Here we show the name, elemental sign, original concentration (%), concentration in solution (ppm), and reference solution concentrations (ppm) from Hoagland (1950).

Pioneer NPK (Mg) Macro Blue 14-3-23 (3)					
Description	Element	Original Concentration (%)	PPM in solution	PPM in solution from Hoagland (1950)	Nutrient Source from Hoagland (1950)
Total Nitrogen	N	14.00%	119	210	NH ₄ H ₂ PO ₄
Nitrate	NO ₃ ⁻	10.40%	88.4		
Ammonium	NH ₄ ⁺	3.60%	30.6		
Water soluble Phosphorous	P	2.90%	24.65	31	See Nitrogen
Citric and water soluble Phosphorous	P	2.90%	24.65		
Water soluble Potassium	K	23.00%	195.5	235	KNO ₃
Water soluble Magnesium	Mg	3.00%	25.5	48.6	MgSO ₄

Water soluble Sulphur	S	3.90%	33.15	64	See Mg
Chloride	Cl	0.50%	4.25	0.65	MnCl ₂
Fluoride	F	0.50%	4.25		
Calcium (CaCO ₃ , Chalk, in Danish Tap Water)	Ca	X	~300	160	Ca(NO ₃) ₂
EC (mS/cm)		1.78			
Pioneer Micro with Iron					
Description	Element	Original Concentration (%)	PPM in solution		
Boron	B	0.23%	0.1955	0.5	H ₃ BO ₃
Copper	Cu	0.14%	0.119	0.02	CuSO ₄
Iron	Fe	1.32%	1.122	5	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ Fe ₂ O ₁₈
Manganese	Mn	0.50%	0.425	0.5	See Chloride
Molybdenum	Mo	0.05%	0.0425	0.011	H ₂ MoO ₄
Zinc	Zn	0.18%	0.153	0.05	ZnSO ₄
EC (mS/cm)		0.006			
Total EC (mS/cm)		1.786			

Table 7. Average pH and EC values of Danish Tap Water at Taastrup Campus, Tap Water with Acid, Tap Water with Fertilizer at 15% dilution, and Tap Water with Fertilizer at 15% dilution and Acid to a pH target of 6.0.

Source	pH	EC
Tap Water	7.23	0.66
Tap Water w/ Acid	6.0	0.77
Tap Water w/ Fertilizer	7.35	1.48
Tap Water w/ Fertilizer and Acid	6.0	1.78

2.6 BIOMASS MEASUREMENTS

For each generation of Microgreens, 8 days after sowing, the entirety of above-substrate plant biomass (cotyledons and stem) was harvested. Fresh Weights (FW) were collected for each complete cup using a gravimetric scale with a sensitivity of $d = 0.01 / 0.001$ g and maximum of 510 g (PG503-S DeltaRange, Mettler Toledo, USA). Figures 9 and 10 show the Microgreens when they are ready for harvest. After the total FW was taken, approximately 10-50 stems were taken (depending on the species) for allocation to Secondary Metabolite analyses, which were then frozen at -20 °C until analysis. The remaining FW value was then noted, and this was used to calculate the remaining percentage of FW, which therefore allowed us to multiply the corresponding Dry Weight (DW) to estimate a total value per cup. The FW samples not allocated to the freezer were then immediately placed in a drying oven for four days at 60 °C. The Dry Weight (DW) was then taken for each sample using the same scale and multiplied by each replicate's corresponding FW percentage value. Dry Weight Percent (DW%) was then calculated as:

$$\text{Dry Weight Percent} = \frac{\text{Dry Weight}}{\text{Fresh Weight}} \times 100$$

Figure 9. Photograph of a generation of Brassicaceae Microgreens at time of harvest; Kale is shown foreground left, Kohlrabi is foreground right, Mustard is middle-ground right, and Radish is background right.

Figure 10. Close-up side view of Brassicaceae Microgreens at time of harvest. Foreground shows Kale Microgreens, with Mustard in the background.

2.7 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Data were analyzed with the statistical software R (version 4.2.1) and corresponding interface R Studio (2022.07.1+554 "Spotted Wakerobin", R Studio, Boston, USA). We used studentized residuals and fitted values, as well as normal quantile plots, to test for normality of data, which was verified. We used a linear model

proceeded by estimated marginal means to demonstrate differences between treatments; results were significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 MUSTARD

3.1.1 FRESH WEIGHT ACCUMULATION

Figure 11 is a facet graph that shows the Fresh Weight accumulation of Mustard Microgreens without fertilizer (no) and with fertilizer (yes) at their respective four seeding densities (lowest to highest: low, standard, middle, high) for all five of our light recipes. The top layer of graphs details the accumulation of FW when divided by the starting seeding density (grams of harvested Fresh Weight per gram of starting seed). This was done to demonstrate the influence of competition when growing Microgreens. Overall, it shows that Mustard Microgreens produced the most relative biomass per seed when they were sown at the lowest density with fertilizer. This relationship was consistent across all four densities, with standard, middle, and high seeding densities having respectively decreasing relative biomass accumulation. The lowercase letters above each light recipe are compact letter displays (CLD) showing the significant differences between light recipes within each graph. The bottom layer of graphs shows Fresh Weight accumulation in kilograms per m². Without fertilization, the best performing light recipe was High Far-Red, which was significantly better than the other four recipes. With fertilization, the best recipe was also the High Far-Red. Interestingly, the cheaper 24VHELEDs performed as well as the HBG, HR, and NG recipes with and without fertilization as they were not significantly different. Figure 11 demonstrates, overall, that the accumulation of fresh biomass in Mustard Microgreens was a function of fertilization, light recipe, and seeding density. The best overall recipe was HFR with fertilization at a low seeding density, although this is spatially less efficient, as it would require additional room for more cups to

produce the same amount of total biomass.

Figure 11. Facet graph detailing the accumulation of Fresh Weight biomass for Mustard Microgreens. The top layer shows FW biomass accumulation as grams of harvested FW per gram of starting seed; the bottom layer shows the FW in kilograms per m². The four left panels show results for No fertilizer at four densities (low, standard, middle, and high seeding densities) and

the right panels show Yes fertilizer at the same four seeding densities. Lowercase letters above their corresponding light recipes detail the significant differences or similarities between light recipes within their respective graphs using the compact letter display (CLD).

Figure 12 shows the improvements in Fresh Weight biomass accumulation when fertilizer was applied as a function of seeding density and light recipe. Values are shown as ‘FW fertilized’ divided by ‘FW non-fertilized’ to demonstrate the relative gains of applying fertilizer. Overall, it shows that for Mustard Microgreens, fertilization had the greatest improvements for the HBG light recipe. Although there are differences between the seeding densities depending on the light recipe, this figure shows that, overall, fertilizer improved fresh biomass accumulation by 1.41 to 1.9 times, making it a good way to improve fresh biomass. Interestingly, the two recipes with the lowest amount of green light, which can penetrate leaves, saw greater improvements in lower seeding densities compared to high seeding densities. This indicates that fertilization is more effective for higher seeding densities with light recipes that have components that can

penetrate leaves, such as Far-Red and Green light.

Figure 12. Figure detailing the improvements to fresh biomass as a result of fertilizer application, as differentiated by seeding density and light recipe.

3.1.2 DRY WEIGHT ACCUMULATION

Figure 13 is also a facet graph detailing dry weight (DW) biomass accumulation, with the same panels and layers as the FW Mustard Microgreens figure above. Overall, the same general relationships were seen, except for a few small differences. For instance, the CLD shows that there were slightly different relationships across the light recipes within each panel. One interesting result was that the lower cost 24VHELEDs performed less well than the higher cost and higher intensity OSRAM lights overall. This is not surprising considering they were producing only around 17% of the PFD compared to the OSRAM lights (see Table 3 above, which shows that the 24VHELEDs produced around 46.09 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, while on average the OSRAM lights produced 270.47 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$). Therefore, more photons were translated into more biomass, as more photosynthesis was able to occur with higher intensity light recipes. Another interesting difference is that without fertilizer, the HFR recipe had a relatively much greater biomass compared to HFR with fertilizer, as indicated by the CLD. Therefore, HGB and HFR were the two best recipes for DW accumulation with fertilization, although HR also performed well at

a lower density. This is not surprising considering that the relative proportions of Green and Far-Red light, both of which penetrate leaves and were higher in the HBG and the HFR recipes, performed the best at high densities. However, the HBG recipe without fertilization performed relatively poorly, even at high density. This figure therefore shows that for DW, there are interactions between light recipe and fertilization for maximization of DW biomass. Interestingly, the NG and the 24VHELEDs were the worst performing light recipes. Furthermore,

for dry weight, there were more differences between seeding densities here, likely reflecting an intolerance to competition. Overall, the best performing recipes were HFR without fertilizer, which was significantly different than the other recipes at high and standard densities, and HBG, HFR, and HR at different densities with fertilization. Another key takeaway is that fertilization did not greatly improve the amount of DW compared to FW improvements, which is shown in the figure below as well.

Figure 13. Facet graph detailing the accumulation of Dry Weight (DW) biomass for Mustard Microgreens. The top layer shows DW biomass accumulation as grams of harvested DW per gram of starting seed; the bottom layer shows the DW in kilograms per m². The four left panels show results for No fertilizer at four densities (low, standard, middle, and high seeding densities) and the right panels show Yes fertilizer at the same four seeding densities. Lowercase letters above their corresponding light recipes detail the significant differences or similarities between light recipes within their respective graphs using the compact letter display (CLD).

Interestingly, for DW fertilizer gain, shown in Figure 14, fertilizer only improved DW accumulation by 1.08 to 1.53 times, depending on the light recipe. This shows a much smaller improvement to DW than to FW via fertilization. Therefore, improvements via fertilization are largely allocated to FW, and not to DW. For producers, this is not a problem, as the product that is consumed is fresh, but it does reveal that improvements in biomass from fertilization have more to do with fresh biomass and not dry biomass.

Figure 14. Figure detailing the improvements to dry biomass as a result of fertilizer application, as differentiated by seeding density and light recipe.

3.1.3 FRESH WEIGHT REGRESSIONS

Figure 15 shows the different average accumulations of fresh biomass for Mustard Microgreens at different seeding densities for each corresponding light recipe. They show that there is a strong positive linear fit between seeding density and fresh biomass production. However, the slope for the fertilized treatment was in general higher than the non-fertilized, indicating that fertilization helped compensate for competition. This was seen as the lower density sowings were relatively close, and then separated further at higher densities when comparing Mustard Microgreens grown with and without fertilization. The only time this wasn't the case was for the HR recipe; this is likely because the Mustard tended to burn when too much Red light was applied, which was more pronounced with the higher seeding densities (more competition). Interestingly, for the 24VHELED, non-fertilized Mustard saw production losses at the highest density, compared to a stable linear

increase with fertilizer.

Figure 15. Regressions detailing the harvested grams per cup of fresh weight biomass. Each panel shows the respective light recipe, with the two different lines showing fertilization (in red) and non-fertilization (in blue) results. Regression equations and R² values are shown to detail the differences between slope and goodness of fit of the regressions.

3.2 KOHLRABI

3.2.1 FRESH WEIGHT ACCUMULATION

Figure 16 is a facet graph that shows the Fresh Weight accumulation of Kohlrabi Microgreens without fertilizer (no) and with fertilizer (yes) at their respective four seeding densities (lowest to highest: low, standard, middle, high) for all five of our light recipes. The top layer of graphs details the accumulation of FW when divided by the starting seeding density (grams of harvested Fresh Weight per gram of starting seed). The top layer shows how competition influences Microgreens. Overall, it shows that Kohlrabi Microgreens produced the most relative biomass per seed when they were sown at the lowest density with fertilizer. However, this relationships was less clear than with Mustard Microgreens. This could be the result of Kohlrabi having a lower seed germination rate. The lowercase letters above each light recipe are compact letter displays (CLD) showing the significant differences between light recipes within each graph. The bottom layer of graphs shows Fresh Weight accumulation in kilograms per m². Without fertilization, the best performing light recipe was High Far-Red, although this was dependent on the seeding density. At the industry standard seeding density, it was significantly different from NG, HR, and 24VHELED light recipes, but it was in the same category as HBG. At high density with no fertilizer, only the NG recipe performed significantly worse compared to the four others. With fertilization, the HFR recipe was also the best, although it was also density dependent, with HBG once again performing almost as well. Interestingly, the cheaper 24VHELEDs performed relatively well without fertilization, but with fertilization, the HFR and HBG recipes were significantly better. Figure 16 demonstrates, overall, that the accumulation of FW in Kohlrabi Microgreens was a function of fertilization, light recipe, and seeding density. The best overall recipe was HFR with fertilization at a low seeding density, with the

Yes:High HFR also relatively high, which would make it the most spatially efficient recipe.

Figure 16. Facet graph detailing the accumulation of Fresh Weight biomass for Kohlrabi Microgreens. The top layer shows FW biomass accumulation as grams of harvested FW per gram of starting seed; the bottom layer shows the FW in kilograms per m². The four left panels show results for No fertilizer at four densities (low, standard, middle, and high seeding densities) and the right panels show Yes fertilizer at the same four seeding densities. Lowercase letters above their corresponding light recipes detail the significant differences or similarities between light recipes within their respective graphs using the compact letter display (CLD).

Figure 17 shows the improvements in Fresh Weight Kohlrabi biomass accumulation when fertilizer was applied as a function of seeding density and light recipe. Values are shown as ‘FW fertilized’ divided by ‘FW non-fertilized’ to show relative gains. Overall, it shows that for Kohlrabi Microgreens, fertilization had the greatest improvements for HBG and NG light recipes. Although there are differences between the seeding densities depending on the light recipe, this figure shows that, overall, fertilizer improves biomass accumulation by 1.35 to 1.92 times, making it a good way to improve fresh biomass accumulation.

Figure 17. Figure detailing the improvements to Kohlrabi fresh biomass as a result of fertilizer application, as differentiated by seeding density and light recipe.

3.2.2 DRY WEIGHT ACCUMULATION

Figure 18 is also a facet graph detailing Dry Weight (DW) biomass accumulation, with the same panels and layers as the FW Kohlrabi Microgreens figure above. Overall, the HFR recipe was the highest as it was for FW, both for fertilized and unfertilized Kohlrabi. Although there were more significant differences in the FW graphs, the DW graphs had fewer significant differences. This indicates that for DW, there was less of an influence of light quality in the light recipes than the light quantity, as only the 24VHELEDs performed significantly worse than the others. One interesting pattern was the Yes:High recipe had relatively lower values in the top panel, indicating that although it produced relative compared fresh biomass, ultimately the high degree of competition reduced the overall DW accumulation at high seeding densities compared to lower seeding densities. Another interesting relationship is shown via the CLD, which demonstrates that there were slightly different relationships across the light recipes within each panel. Furthermore, once again the lower

cost 24VHELEDs performed less well than the higher cost and higher intensity OSRAM lights overall, as it was significantly less productive than the other four recipes overall. As mentioned in the Mustard section above, this is not surprising considering that this recipe produced a much lower PFD.

Figure 18. Facet graph detailing the accumulation of Dry Weight biomass for Kohlrabi Microgreens. The top layer shows DW biomass accumulation as grams of harvested DW per gram of starting seed; the bottom layer shows the DW in kilograms per m². The four left panels show results for No fertilizer at four densities (low, standard, middle, and high seeding densities) and the right panels show Yes fertilizer at the same four seeding densities. Lowercase letters above their corresponding light recipes detail the significant differences or similarities between light recipes within their respective graphs using the compact letter display (CLD).

Interestingly, for DW fertilizer gain, shown in Figure 19, fertilizer only improved DW accumulation by 1.11 to 1.54 times, depending on the light recipe. This shows a much smaller improvement to DW than to FW via fertilization. Therefore, improvements via fertilization are largely allocated to FW, and not to DW. Just as for FW, the greatest improvements were seen for the NG and HBG recipes.

Figure 19. Figure detailing the improvements to dry biomass as a result of fertilizer application, as differentiated by seeding density and light recipe.

3.2.3 FRESH WEIGHT REGRESSIONS

Figure 20 shows the accumulation of fresh biomass for Kohlrabi at different seeding densities for each corresponding light recipe. They show that there is a relatively strong positive linear fit between seeding density and fresh biomass production. However, the slope for the fertilized treatment was in general higher than the no-fertilizer, indicating that fertilization helped control for competition dynamics. This was seen as the lower density sowings were relatively close, and then separated further at higher densities when comparing Kohlrabi Microgreens grown with and without fertilization. This was the case for all five light recipes tested in our experimental trials. One interesting result here is the plateauing of the Kohlrabi when grown without fertilizer at a high density with the 24VHELEDs. Considering its low PFD, lack of Far-Red light, and lack of fertilizer, it is

not surprising to see some tapering off of production, as the final point at the highest sowing density is falling off the regression line.

Figure 20. Figures detailing the harvested grams per cup of fresh weight biomass. Each panel shows the respective light recipe, with the two different lines showing fertilization (in red) and non-fertilization (in blue) results. Regression equations and R^2 values are shown to detail the differences between slope and goodness of fit of the regressions.

3.3 RADISH

3.3.1 FRESH WEIGHT ACCUMULATION

For Radish Fresh Weight (FW) biomass production, the best light recipe without fertilizer was the HFR (Figure 21). This was significantly different from the 24VHELED and the NG light recipes, but the HBG and the HR recipes were not significantly different to the HFR; furthermore, the 24VHELEDs were significantly lower than the NG recipe. This was the same for all four seeding densities. For Radish FW biomass production with fertilizer, the best light recipe was also HFR, which was also significantly different from the 24VHELED and the NG light recipes, but not the HBG and the HR recipes; once again, the 24VHELED recipe was significantly lower than the NG. This was also true for all four seeding densities. In general, the top layer of graphs, which shows the relative production of fresh biomass per gram of starting seed, demonstrated that once again the low density seeding produced the most relative biomass. This was the same with and without fertilizer. Overall, we see again that the best overall recipe is the HFR, with and without fertilizer.

Figure 21. Facet graph detailing the accumulation of Fresh Weight biomass for Radish Microgreens. The top layer shows FW biomass accumulation as grams of harvested FW per gram of starting seed; the bottom layer shows the FW in kilograms per m^2 . The four left panels show results for No fertilizer at four densities (low, standard, middle, and high seeding densities) and the right panels show Yes fertilizer at the same four seeding densities. Lowercase letters above their corresponding light recipes detail the significant differences or similarities between light recipes within their respective graphs using the compact letter display (CLD).

Figure 22 shows the Radish FW fertilizer gain (fertilized FW / non-fertilized FW). Overall, it demonstrates a similar pattern to the other species, with around a 1.4 to 1.81 times improvement in fresh biomass production as a result of fertilization. Interestingly, Mustard, Kohlrabi, and Radish all showed similar density responses to fertilization improvements for each light recipe. That is, the standard density generally had a better response to fertilization than the higher density seedings, except for the HR recipe, where the high density showed the greatest improvements in fresh biomass accumulation. Furthermore, the NG recipe showed that the standard density had a very positive response to fertilization, while the high density did not. This is likely because of the total lack of green light component in this recipe; at high densities, green light can potentially mitigate against competition by penetrating canopy leaves to offer some useful light for subcanopy leaves. The NG recipe having no green light, and having a much lower response to fertilizer at a high seeding density, for all three species, supports this.

Figure 22. Figure detailing the improvements to fresh biomass as a result of fertilizer application, as differentiated by seeding density and light recipe.

3.3.2 DRY WEIGHT ACCUMULATION

For Radish Dry Weight (DW) biomass accumulation, we see a more dynamic pattern in Figure 23. For instance, there are distinct patterns for fertilizer application. Without fertilizer, the best light recipe was HR. However, this was not significantly different from the HFR light recipe at any seeding density. Once again, the 24VHELED recipe with the lowest light intensity (PFD) had the lowest DW; this was significantly lower than all other light recipes at all seeding densities. With fertilization, the 24VHELED recipe was also the worst performing for DW, and it was significantly lower than the other four recipes. With fertilization at a high density, all four OSRAM recipes were statistically the same, although the HBG was the overall best performing recipe. At a lower density, the HBG recipe was significantly better than the HFR, although it was in the same category as the NG and NG recipes. Across seeding densities for the relative DW production, the same relationships were

observed whereby the lowest seeding density produced the most relative dry biomass. This was the same with and without fertilization. Interestingly, the Radish DW had very similar results to the Mustard DW, where each showed a fertilizer and light recipe interaction. That is, the HBG was lower without fertilizer, and performed much better with fertilizer for DW production.

Figure 23. Facet graph detailing the accumulation of Dry Weight biomass for Radish Microgreens. The top layer shows DW biomass accumulation as grams of harvested DW per gram of starting seed; the bottom layer shows the DW in kilograms per m^2 . The four left panels show results for No fertilizer at four densities (low, standard, middle, and high seeding densities) and the right panels show Yes fertilizer at the same four seeding densities. Lowercase letters above their corresponding light recipes detail the significant differences or similarities between light recipes within their respective graphs using the compact letter display (Tukey's HSD).

As is consistent with the other species, Radish DW fertilizer gain saw improvements around 1.03 to 1.26 times due to fertilizer application (Figure 24). Overall, this demonstrates again that much of the biomass accumulation as a result of fertilizer application went to FW accumulation, as the DW fertilizer gains were much lower than the FW gains. A similar seeding density response was also seen, where the lower seeding densities did slightly better in the HR and NG recipes, which was also seen for the FW.

Figure 24. Figure detailing the improvements to dry biomass as a result of fertilizer application, as differentiated by seeding density and light recipe.

3.3.3 FRESH WEIGHT REGRESSIONS

The below figures demonstrate the FW biomass accumulation for Radish Microgreens as a result of their seeding density and light recipe (Figure 25). Overall, it shows that fertilization helped buffer against the competition of higher densities, as the greater fertilized regression slopes demonstrates. There was a very good fit (R^2) for the regression equations overall. It is interesting to note that the NG recipe was the only one that did not see a much greater improvement in FW biomass accumulation as a result of fertilization. This is not surprising considering that the NG light recipe had less light recipe components that could penetrate the leaves in the PAR range; having these penetrative components in a light recipe can buffer against competition by allowing useful light to pass through the canopy layer into the sub-canopy layers for use. As we've seen for Mustard and Kohlrabi, Radish Microgreens also saw a more pronounced decrease in production at higher densities for the 24VHELEDs with no fertilizer compared to those grown with fertilizer. A lack of fertilization

therefore decreases tolerance for competition at high densities.

Figure 25. Figures detailing the harvested grams per cup of fresh weight biomass. Each panel shows the respective light recipe, with the two different lines showing fertilization (in red) and non-fertilization (in blue) results. Regression equations and R² values are shown to detail the differences between slope and goodness of fit of the regressions.

3.4 KALE

3.4.1 FRESH WEIGHT ACCUMULATION

For Kale Fresh Weight (FW) biomass accumulation, there were no significantly different recipes without fertilization (Figure 26). With fertilization, all three OSRAM light recipes were significantly better than the 24VHELED recipe at high density. At the standard seeding density, only the HBG recipe was significantly better than any of the other recipes (24VHELED). The HR and NG were not significantly different from the HBG and 24VHELED, however. For seeding density responses to relative biomass production, we saw the same relationship as before, where the lowest density produced the greatest relative biomass, for both fertilized and

unfertilized Kale Microgreens.

Figure 26. Facet graph detailing the accumulation of Fresh Weight biomass for Kale Microgreens. The top layer shows FW biomass accumulation as grams of harvested FW per gram of starting seed; the bottom layer shows the FW in kilograms per m². The four left panels show results for No fertilizer at four densities (low, standard, middle, and high seeding densities) and the right panels show Yes fertilizer at the same four seeding densities. Lowercase letters above their corresponding light recipes detail the significant differences or similarities between light recipes within their respective graphs using the compact letter display (CLD).

Figure 27 shows the improvements in FW biomass accumulation as a function of light recipe and seeding density for Kale Microgreens. Overall, it shows that fertilizer improved FW biomass accumulation by about 1.40 times up to 2.02 times; the best improvements were seen for the HBG recipe, as it was for the other Brassicaceae Microgreens, and the lowest improvements were seen for 24VHELED. This lack of response could be due to the lower overall light intensity of the 24VHELEDs. Overall, the high density Kale with the HBG light recipe saw the greatest improvements as a result of fertilization.

Figure 27. Figure detailing the improvements to fresh biomass as a result of fertilizer application, as differentiated by seeding density and light recipe.

3.4.2 DRY WEIGHT ACCUMULATION

As we've seen for the other three species, the 24VHELED light recipe produced significantly lower DW biomass than the other OSRAM light recipes for Kale Microgreens (Figure 28). This is likely the result of its overall lower PFD. Without fertilization, there were significant differences between 24VHELED and the HBG and the NG, but not the HR recipe. This was the same for all densities. With fertilization, however, we found that all three OSRAM recipes were significantly greater than the 24VHELED recipe, at all densities. Furthermore, the same basic structure of relative biomass production was seen, where the lowest density produced the highest relative biomass, and the highest density produced the lowest relative biomass. However, in units of kg/m², the best production was for the highest density. Therefore, as with all the other species grown here, there is a trade-off between relative production and spatial availability. That is, although there is more relative production at

lower seeding densities, this requires more space, including more lights, growing space, and corresponding materials.

Figure 28. Facet graph detailing the accumulation of Dry Weight biomass for Kale Microgreens. The top layer shows DW biomass accumulation as grams of harvested DW per gram of starting seed; the bottom layer shows the DW in kilograms per m². The four left panels show results for No fertilizer at four densities (low, standard, middle, and high seeding densities) and the right panels show Yes fertilizer at the same four seeding densities. Lowercase letters above their corresponding light recipes detail the significant differences or similarities between light recipes within their respective graphs using the compact letter display (CLD).

Figure 29 shows the gains in Kale DW biomass accumulation as a result of light recipe and seeding density. Overall, it shows that Kale saw DW improvements of 1.17 times to 1.43 times due to the application of fertilizer for Kale Microgreens. The lowest responses were seen in the 24VHELED recipe, and the highest improvements were seen in the HR recipe.

Figure 29. Figure detailing the improvements to dry biomass as a result of fertilizer application, as differentiated by seeding density and light recipe.

3.4.3 FRESH WEIGHT REGRESSIONS

The panels in Figure 30 below show the accumulation of Kale FW biomass across densities and light recipes, with separate regression lines for fertilized (in red) and non-fertilized Kale Microgreens (in blue). Overall, it shows that for all light recipes, the fertilizer mitigated the effect of competition by improving the higher density production values compared to the non-fertilized ones. The HBG saw the greatest relative improvements with the largest slope for the regression equation with fertilizer application, while the 24VHELED showed the smallest fertilizer improvement. Interestingly, for Kale, we also experimented on a final seeding density, which was higher, proportionally, than the other four densities for the other species. At 4 grams per cup seeding density, which is beyond the regular range for the other species, we found that the production began to diminish, as seen in the 24VHELED figure. Not only did production diminish, it even went negative compared to the lower seeding densities when the Kale was not fertilized. When it was fertilized at this highest density, it did not lose as much production, but it was still relatively reduced. This demonstrates a general acceptable range of seeding densities for Kale, and perhaps for the others as well, as beyond 50% higher seeding

rates from the standard seems to be the upper limit. Past this threshold, even for fertilized Microgreens, seems to result in a relative loss in production, as the gain is no longer linear. However, fertilization does seem to mitigate against this slightly, as seen below.

Figure 30. Figures detailing the harvested grams per cup of fresh weight biomass. Each panel shows the respective light recipe, with the two different lines showing fertilization (in red) and non-fertilization (in blue) results. Regression equations and R² values are shown to detail the differences between slope and goodness of fit of the regressions.

3.5 COST ACCOUNTING

The previous sections detailed the overall production metrics for FW and DW biomass accumulation for all four Brassicaceae Microgreens as a function of seeding density, fertilizer, and light recipe. Another important lens through which to view the usability of the investigated environmental recipes in this study is to include a basic reference value for the cost. In this regard, Figures 31 and 32 demonstrate the amount of FW and DW biomass, respectively, produced per area per 1000 USD. For instance, Figure 31 shows that the 24VHELED, although it had lower overall production values compared to the four OSRAM light recipes, it produced much more biomass per unit input (USD). It is important to contextualize the results of these experiments by noting that all recipes had the same baseline background inputs such as a climate chamber, equipment, fertilizer, grow system, etc. Therefore, the only difference was the use of different types of lights. We have shown previously that there are significant differences between the response of Brassicaceae Microgreens to different light recipes, fertilization, and seeding densities, but these do not reflect the much different input costs. The 24VHELEDs, although slightly less productive, are significantly cheaper. Table 8 below demonstrates the scope

of this difference, illustrating that for FW, the production of biomass per unit area per 1000 USD was around 50 times higher compared to the OSRAM light recipes. For DW, it was about the same as well, although slightly lower. This demonstrates that there are tradeoffs between production and inputs required. Furthermore, we have also shown that there is a higher relative production of Microgreens when they are sown at lower densities; however, this would require more space to produce them. For instance, to match the gross production of the high seeding density per area, a standard seeding density would need to have 1.43 times the overall growing space for around a 10% improvement in relative biomass production. This would therefore

multiply the growing area needed, including lights and other corresponding necessary equipment and setup by 1.43 as well. Furthermore, Table 9 shows that the OSRAM lights, although they had around 7 times the PFD, only improved FW and DW biomass production by an average of around 1.13 and 1.23 times, respectively. Considering they are around 50 times less cost efficient, this small improvement in production is not worth the cost.

Figure 31. Figure detailing the production of fresh biomass per unit area per 1000 US dollars. This is shown for each light recipe with and without fertilizer.

Figure 32. Figure detailing the production of dry biomass per unit area per 1000 US dollars. This is shown for each light recipe with and without fertilizer.

Table 8. Comparison of 24VHELED relative production (FW or DW kg/m² per 1000 USD) compared to average values for the other four light recipes (OSRAM). Values derived from Figures 31 and 32 above.

FRESH WEIGHT					
SPECIES	Kale	Kohlrabi	Mustard	Radish	Total
TOTAL	55.71	55.09	54.19	50.22	53.11
NO FERTILIZER	53.60	52.81	51.17	45.34	48.72
YES FERTILIZER	57.23	49.26	48.87	47.18	49.51
DRY WEIGHT					
TOTAL	55.15	44.73	49.18	47.54	49.28
NO FERTILIZER	52.63	43.38	45.11	42.87	45.14
YES FERTILIZER	57.50	41.88	48.45	48.54	49.30

Table 9. Overall improvements to biomass production for Fresh Weight (FW) and Dry Weight (DW) for averaged OSRAM light recipe values compared to 24VHELED values.

Fertilizer:Species	FW	DW
No Fertilizer Total	1.10	1.22
Kale	1.00	1.09
Kohlrabi	1.08	1.31
Mustard	1.09	1.21
Radish	1.22	1.28
Yes Fertilizer Total	1.16	1.23
Kale	1.18	1.23
Kohlrabi	1.16	1.35

Mustard	1.13	1.16
Radish	1.18	1.17

4 CONCLUSIONS

We have shown here that there is no single optimal environmental recipe for the Brassicaceae Microgreens we experimented with here in D1.2. There are inherent production tradeoffs that we have outlined, with outcomes depending on different environmental inputs. For instance, we have shown the advantages of using expensive highly programmable lights, but their production per unit input (in UDS dollars) is around 50 times less efficient than the cheap, easily installed 24VHELEDs. In this regard, we have shown that whether there are significant gains in expensive lights compared to cheaper ones should be contextualized with their degree of difference in accordance with their price, energy usage and degree of labor input required for successful user operation. We believe that future research should continue in this avenue of comparing low-tech and high-tech inputs to determine what the gains are in biomass accumulation per unit input (including water and energy), as current research focuses on highly sophisticated technologies and techniques, while some commercial farmers still rely on very simple setups. The ultimate goal is not to maximize yield, but to do so efficiently with minimal inputs. For instance, Table 9 above demonstrates that although the OSRAM lights produced 1.13 times the FW, and around 1.23 times the DW compared to the 24VHELEDs, they cost over 50 times more to produce equivalent biomass. Over time this dynamic could shift, but many Microgreens are sold by the cup, so these small improvements wouldn't necessarily even be noticeable. Furthermore, the minor benefit in OSRAM production is further diminished by the fact that the OSRAM lights produced around 7 times the PFD, and yet only improved biomass by a small margin (1.13 and 1.23 for FW and DW, respectively); the 24VHELEDs are therefore much more energy efficient as well, as they produced around 7 times fewer photons but had only a slightly smaller biomass production. Another important point is that the OSRAM lights do not produce homogenous light conditions, while the 24VHELEDs do. Finally, the 24VHELEDs require very little upkeep or labor required for installation and use, unlike the OSRAM lights, which are unwieldy and easily malfunction. Overall, we can make a strong case that the 24VHELEDs, which are readily available, require no programming, and are relatively cheap, are the best choice for growers. For Microgreens which can be grown in the form of a vertical farm, this could be even more efficient, as the 24VHELEDs produce little heat, and weigh almost nothing, at around 350 grams per layer, compared to the OSRAM lights, which are around 9 kg for each panel (27 kgs per layer), which requires special attachments and security for successful use.

Although we have shown that there are some small species-specific responses, we found that overall, the best light recipe, regardless of fertilizer application or cost considerations, was the HFR (an OSRAM light recipe). This is not surprising considering recent research on the effects of Far-Red light on plant growth and its many benefits on plant physiology and morphology (Zhen and van Iersel 2017; Park and Runkle 2017; Zhang et al. 2019; Yang et al 2020). This light component is increasingly becoming recognized as an essential horticultural tool, especially for vertical farming. We have shown here evidence supporting this claim. This is even more so the case for Microgreens considering their young phenological stage; they are likely not photosynthesizing to a high degree, and therefore could benefit more from photomorphogenesis cues from E-PAR light signals, such as those from Far-Red light. Furthermore, these Microgreens were exposed to light after only four days of

germinating in the dark. Therefore, their degree of photosynthetic activity is lower than more mature plants. It is likely that photomorphogenesis plays a key role at this early stage, which therefore means that using light outside the PAR range, such as Far-Red light, can have potential positive benefits for the young Microgreens, especially as Far-Red light results in morphological cues that increase height gains, which is valuable for Microgreens production. This occurs via Far-Red light stimulating height gains by signaling a 'shade avoidance' response. This could prompt the young Microgreens to allocate energy to height gains and above ground biomass. Considering the short growing cycle of only 8 days, this is a strategy that could benefit growers. For our study here, we found that there were significant height gains (data not shown) for the HFR recipe compared to others with lower Far-Red percentages.

However, the cost of the specific HFR recipe, achieved by the OSRAM lights, makes it prohibitive for wide-scale use by producers. The OSRAM lights are overall not worth the trouble: there were programming difficulties, software failures, weight problems, and they are hugely expensive (over 2,000 Euros per panel, with a very limited and inconsistent light footprint). We can therefore with high probability of success recommend the use of high efficiency 24-volt LEDs, from a variety of suppliers (our supplier was a general one). If we were to make any suggested improvements to the 24VHELEDs, it would be to increase the amount of Far-Red light in the 24VHELED recipe, as well as suggest an increase in PFD if high densities are used without fertilizer. We therefore recommend the use of low-cost LEDs, and ideally those that have a high component of Far-Red, as well as a Green light component. Green light is valuable for a few key reasons, such as its ability to penetrate leaves and enter the sub-canopy spaces for use by lower layer leaves; it is also important for cueing plant's circadian rhythms, which is essential for appropriate physiological activities (Battle & Jones, 2020). Research on Green light is still in its nascency, with some authors noting that there is a dearth of knowledge around Green photoreceptors in plants (e.g., Christie et al., 2015). By deliberately focusing on recipes with and without Green light, we have helped demonstrate its use in different degrees of competitive environments. In general, our results showed a very poor performance for our No Green light recipe compared to the others, as it was either the worst or the second worst for our Brassicaceae Microgreens.

For fertilization, we found that there were significant improvements for FW and DW biomass production. This was much more pronounced overall for FW than it was for DW. We have shown that there was around a 1.4 to 2 times improvement in FW, and around 1.1 to 1.5 times improvement for DW accumulation as a result of fertilization. Furthermore, we have shown with our linear regression in sections 3.1.3, 3.2.3, 3.3.3, and 3.4.3, that fertilization buffered against competition at high densities. This was seen via these improvements having a higher slope than the non-fertilized treatments. Overall, these improvements were linear, and they only differed by slope. Interestingly, the only place where we saw reductions in productivity outside of this linear function was with the 24VHELEDs at high densities without fertilizer. This is not surprising considering that the 24VHELEDs had 7 times lower rates of PFD; the lower levels of light combined with lack of fertilization resulted in a loss of productivity. For the OSRAM light recipes, which had much higher PFD (around 270 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$), the higher densities were more in line with the linear function. Therefore, we have shown that there

is an interaction between fertilizer, light recipe, and seeding density. Overall, we have shown that the high seeding density was adequate for Microgreens grown without fertilization for the OSRAM recipes, as we did not see plateauing or loss of productivity. However, in sum, fertilization does improve production at these higher densities in comparison to the non-fertilized Microgreens. If possible, fertilization is therefore recommended. One final point is that adding fertilization does add labor inputs because of preparing the solution and needing to more intensively managing the pH, which must be kept within a certain range for the correct uptake of the nutrients in the solution.

For seeding density, we found that there was a linear response in productivity based on the number of seeds used for sowing, whose slope was dependent on whether they were fertilized or not. There was generally a very strong linear fit for those treatments that received all four seeding densities (lowest R^2 being 0.68, and the highest being 1.00). Our standard seeding densities were selected by information from our seed supplier. We lowered this standard starting value by 25% for our low density, raised it by 25% for our middle density, and raised it again by 25% for our high density (the high density being 50% higher than the standard density). For all these sowing densities, we found a consistent production of biomass that increased linearly. However, for Kale, we took the seeding density one step further, increasing it by 25% again; for this seeding density, seen in Figure 30, we see a marked loss of productivity at this highest density. This was modified by whether or not the Kale was fertilized, which is not surprising considering our previous results detailing how fertilizer improved high density seeding densities compared to those with no fertilizer. Despite this relative positive improvement, it was still below the regression line, and we can therefore see at this final highest density a point where returns diminish regarding seeding density. We therefore can recommend a likely upper limit of our seeding densities at around 50% higher than the standard density; as mentioned previously, however, this is likely dependent on the PFD of the light recipes used, as we saw an overall smaller slope in the linear function for the 24VHELEDs compared to the OSRAM recipes when fertilizer was not used. Another suggestion based on our results is that if fertilization is not an option, it is likely that using a lower seeding density would be more effective overall, as we showed that the relative production of No:Low can be comparable to Yes:High, especially for DW accumulation. As we've mentioned before, however, using lower densities does come at the cost of being less spatially efficient.

Overall, considering the different types of results here for relative biomass, total biomass, and cost accounting as a result of seeding density, fertilization, and light recipe, we have shown that there are inherent tradeoffs when producing Brassicaceae Microgreens. For instance, although the low seeding densities were more relatively productive, they require 1.43 times the space compared to high seeding densities to produce equivalent biomass. In combination with the evident success of HFR and HBG recipes, each of which had high components of light that can penetrate the Microgreen leaf canopies, we recommend that light recipes that use high components of Far-Red and Green light be used in combination with high densities for optimal production. Furthermore, we recommend a light recipe similar to that used for the 24VHELEDs, with a high proportion of Green and Red light (46.45, and 34.02%, respectively); 24VHELEDs with a similar recipe is much

more cost-efficient, energy efficient, space efficient and labor efficient to use. The OSRAM lights have allowed us to show how changing light components within a recipe with the same overall PFD does have significant results on Microgreen production, but it is not a pragmatic solution for growers, and should not be used. Future analyses on secondary metabolites, which will be presented in a future deliverable, will help expand the scope of these dynamics and identify more tradeoffs between biomass and secondary metabolites via light recipe, fertilization, and seeding density changes.

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